

Impact of educational short messages on the level of knowledge on prevention and early detection of tuberculosis from pharmacies in two districts of Peru

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Abstract

This study aimed to evaluate the change in the level of knowledge that pharmacy workers have about tuberculosis after an educational intervention based on sending short message service (SMS) and WhatsApp messages. A prospective study was conducted on a random sample of pharmacies and drugstores in two districts of Lima and Chiclayo using SMS messages. Different stages of preparation (pilot study) of text messages, pre-testing, and content evaluation; implementation and selection of pharmacies; and evaluation of an exit survey to measure the variation in knowledge about tuberculosis were carried out. A total of 132 respondents were surveyed in the final stage, with a median age of 27 years (IQR: 23 to 30); 78.46% were female. Regarding knowledge about epidemiology, diagnosis, and treatment at baseline, the average correct answers were 66.33%, 62.22%, and 54.44%, respectively. Of the total, only 45.45% had a score above the 55th percentile of correct scores. Changes were found in the prevention knowledge score (72.55 vs. 66.33, $p = 0.027$) in the group that read the messages. There were differences in the overall knowledge level of those who read the messages ($p = 0.034$). In conclusion, pharmacy workers have adequate knowledge about tuberculosis, but significant gaps persist in their knowledge regarding treatment. The level of TB knowledge of pharmacy and pharmacy staff improved after an SMS text message-based intervention.

Keywords

tuberculosis, SMS, Peru, primary care, infection, pharmacy

Introduction

In Latin America, Peru accounts for 30% of the estimated cases of extensively drug-resistant tuberculosis (XDR-TB) in the region, and Peru has one of the highest tuberculosis

(TB) rates in the Americas (106 per 100,000 population) (Soto Cabezas MG et al. 2020). The government's commitment to combating this problem is evidenced by the 600% increase in the budget allocated to this disease between 2004 and 2011. Despite this, Peru goes against the global

trend that TB prevalence declines with economic growth. Peru's Human Development Index (HDI) has increased, but the mortality rate of tuberculosis remains high in Peru (Castañeda-Hernández et al. 2013) and Brazil (Santos DT et al. 2018).

Despite being the second leading infectious cause of death after HIV worldwide, TB research has not yet fully exploited the potential of cell phones in health (m-health) (Ali and Prins 2020; Tumuhimbise and Musiimenta 2021).

Many patients find private pharmacies more accessible to visit, as they have longer opening hours and are in more locations than health centers. This makes pharmacies the first point of contact for patients who are reluctant to visit health centers on their own (Fathima et al. 2013).

The role of pharmacies as the first point of contact with patients has been lever-aged in multiple interventions aimed at reaching underserved populations. When provided with adequate training, pharmacy workers have proven to be valuable partners in screening for a variety of conditions, including chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) (Fathima et al. 2013), sleep disorders (Basheti et al. 2021), diabetes, cardiovascular disease (Alzubaidi et al. 2019), and sexually transmitted diseases. The latter was conducted in Peru and showed that pharmacy workers can provide recommendations for specific conditions (García et al. 2012).

Adequate knowledge of pharmacy staff about the prevention and diagnosis of tuberculosis is an important point that could help to control this disease, which is why quick and economical interventions should be sought to help improve knowledge. Therefore, the objective of this work is to evaluate the change in the level of knowledge of pharmacy workers after an educational intervention based on sending SMS.

Material and methods

Design and population

A prospective, analytical study was carried out, with before-and-after evaluation, to evaluate the impact of an intervention based on the use of SMS messages on the level of knowledge about tuberculosis of workers in pharmacies in the districts of Lima and Chiclayo.

In Lima, the study was conducted in the district of Breña belonging to the DISAV Lima city. Breña was chosen because it is a district with an increasing rate of tuberculosis cases and has not been routinely intervened in. In Chiclayo, Lambayeque Province, 493 cases of tuberculosis (87 extrapulmonary and 406 pulmonary) were registered in 2015. The districts of La Victoria and José Leonardo Ortiz are districts of Chiclayo (located at 30 meters above sea level) considered areas of medium-low economic class, with rural areas in extreme poverty and a high incidence (23%) and prevalence of pulmonary tuberculosis.

Intervention

The intervention was carried out in four phases:

1. Preliminary: Information was collected that could serve as a baseline for further implementation of SMS delivery. A pilot survey was implemented to tailor the text messages, and content validity was provided.
2. Preparation: Text messages and a final questionnaire were generated based on the results of the previous phase.
3. Implementation: Pharmacy workers in Chiclayo and Lima received information to participate and were enrolled in the study; text messages were sent to them after the entrance survey. Messages were sent as SMS on the phone as text messages or by WhatsApp service, depending on the participant's choice.
4. Evaluation: Once the intervention was completed, an exit survey was taken to measure the variation in TB knowledge in both the intervention and control groups, and the data were analyzed and prepared for dissemination.

Sampling

The unit of analysis was each worker in the selected pharmacies, including all those who agreed to participate in the study and who had been working in the pharmacy for at least three months.

Epidat was used to calculate the sample size and Stata 15.0 for the analysis of the results. A confidence level of 95%, an alpha error of 5%, a beta error of 20%, and a total sample size of 66 participants were calculated based on the pilot survey.

Data analysis

Univariate descriptive analysis was initially performed using descriptive statistics, averages, and standard deviations in quantitative variables and proportions in qualitative variables.

The efficacy of the intervention was evaluated through the variation in the score of the questionnaire in the 17 knowledge questions themselves, assigning a binary score of correct or incorrect for all of them, and the value of nine correct answers was taken as the cut-off point to define a passing score.

The concepts currently used by the National Health Strategy for Tuberculosis Prevention and Control and the contents of the national TB standard were used to prepare the knowledge questionnaire covering the topics shown in the following diagram. Baseline information was collected with the entry survey.

The intervention was evaluated in two phases: a first phase to assess acceptance and level of knowledge, and a second phase to assess posttest knowledge.

Basic information and knowledge about prevention (five questions), diagnosis (three questions), treatment

(nine questions), and perceptions of knowledge about tuberculosis were collected. An SMS intervention was carried out for 15 days, and after one month, the participants were surveyed again. Paired Student's *t* tests were performed for scores on knowledge and McNemar for proportions on perception of knowledge. A *p* value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical aspects

The confidentiality of the participants was always assured. However, the educational intervention was considered risk-free for them. Verbal, informed consent was given. Participants could choose to leave the study at any stage. All participants were of legal age. Participants could also choose to stop receiving messages on their cell phones at any time. The Hospital Regional Lambayeque approved the execution of the study.

The privacy of the participants' information and confidentiality were ensured through a system of codes accessible only to some researchers. The databases were kept separately because, although it is not patient information, the social stigma related to TB was considered.

Results

A baseline survey was conducted with 63 people in Lima and 31 people in Chiclayo who met the requirements and inclusion criteria.

Results of the baseline survey in Lima and Chiclayo

In general, more workers were women; the mean age was 28.7 ± 9.2 years, and 85.7% belonged to apothecaries. The workers considered that the most frequent symptom of tuberculosis was cough (92.1%), and the most useful diagnostic test to detect it was the sputum test (71.4%). The mean number of knowledge scores was 11.6 ± 1.7 out of a possible 17. In total, 55.32% had correct answers; this behaved in very similar proportions for Lima and Chiclayo ($p = 0.560$). Workers in pharmacies and drugstores had better knowledge of TB prevention and diagnosis, but there are still important gaps in knowledge regarding treatment. Table 1 provides more information on the sociodemographic data.

However, the Lima group had already received a higher percentage of TB information (46.03% vs. 12.90%), which is why it was decided to carry out the intervention in the city of Chiclayo for the second phase.

Results of the intervention

A total of 66 people were surveyed, with a median age of 27 years (RIC: 23 to 30); 78.46% were women. Regarding knowledge about prevention, diagnosis, and treatment at the beginning of the study, the average correct answers were

Table 1. Characteristics of workers in pharmacies in Lima and Chiclayo in the baseline survey.

Characteristics	Lima		Chiclayo		Total n	% p*
	n	%	n	%		
Sex						0.380
Male	15	23.8	9	29.1	24	24.73
Female	48	76.2	22	70.9	70	75.27
Profession						0.785
Pharmacy technician	43	68.25	19	61.29	62	65.96
Pharmaceutical chemist	9	14.29	5	16.13	14	14.89
Other	11	17.46	7	22.58	18	19.15
You consider yourself part of the health system						0.103
Yes	58	92.06	25	80.65	83	86.35
No	5	7.94	6	19.35	11	13.65
You previously received TB information from health care providers						0.001
Yes	29	46.03	4	12.90	33	29.47
No	34	53.97	27	87.10	61	70.53
Frequency of responses						0.560
Correct	35	55.6	17	54.8	52	55.32
Incorrect	28	44.4	14	45.2	42	44.68

* Group homogeneity hypothesis test.

66.33%, 62.22%, and 54.44%, respectively. Of the total, only 45.45% scored above the 55th percentile of correct scores. Six people (9%) could not be found at the end of the study.

Changes were found in the prevention knowledge score (72.33 vs. 66.33; $p = 0.027$) in the group that read the messages. There was a marginal difference in knowledge of diagnosis and treatment. At the end of the study, 52.27% of those who had read the messages scored above the 55th percentile of correct scores. This difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.034$) with respect to those who did not read any messages.

Table 2 shows the information regarding the changes in correct answers, finding significant changes in questions on prevention; with respect to diagnosis and the total score of correct answers, there was an improvement in the score, although with a statistically marginal increase. The self-perception of adequate knowledge improved significantly after the intervention (10.17% vs. 31.67%, $p < 0.001$).

Table 2. Comparison of pre- and post-intervention knowledge levels.

	Pre-intervention X (SD)	Post-intervention X (SD)	p
Percentage of correct answers in prevention	66.33 (2.62)	72.33 (2.33)	0.027
Percentage of correct answers in diagnosis	62.22 (2.79)	69.54 (3.19)	0.056
Percentage of correct answers in treatment	54.44 (1.88)	56.66 (2.29)	0.353
Percentage of correct answers total	59.31 (1.53)	63.13 (2.05)	0.064
Perception of knowledge	n (%)	n (%)	<0.001
Adequate	6 (10.17%)	19 (31.67%)	
Inadequate	53 (89.93%)	41 (68.33%)	

* X = mean. SD = standard deviation.

All respondents stated that they were satisfied with the intervention and would recommend it to other colleagues of theirs.

Discussion

SMS reminder systems for TB patients have been well received due to the ubiquity of the devices and the favorable perception of them. However, the use of SMS has not yet been effectively utilized in the TB prevention stage.

The level of adequate knowledge does not differ much from some other experiences carried out in Peru in other health worker sectors, such as community agents or primary care personnel (Minnery et al. 2013).

In a 2013 study of 301 workers from 66 health centers, most errors were identified related to the consequences of incomplete or inadequate treatment, recognizing MDR-TB, and how often to follow up with sputum testing. Only 50.39% of the participants were able to correctly identify all consequences of incorrect treatment, and only 42.17% were able to properly define MDR-TB (Minnery et al. 2013). The treatment aspects were also more difficult for our study population, which may be because professionals working in pharmacies and drugstores are not familiar with the treatment regimens used in health centers.

Another study carried out in “El Agustino” on health care providers showed clear differences in the level of knowledge among different health care workers depending on their professional training or not, with higher knowledge scores obtained in the group of professionals (Garcia PJ et al. 2018). In our study, pharmaceutical scientists represented a group drawn from the sample to make comparisons between personnel with university education and those without. Gaps in knowledge were in the identification of patients at high risk for TB, the assessment of appropriate treatment, and the consequences of treatment failure (Garcia PJ et al. 2018).

This is the first time that informative messages on resistant tuberculosis have been used by pharmacy personnel in the interior of our country. The results show a minor positive effect, with some threats to internal validity that could provide alternative explanations for the positive effect of the messages.

There are gaps in knowledge related to how to avoid tuberculosis transmission, and people continue to believe myths about disease transmission.

The characteristics of pharmacy workers in Peru have been described in previous studies of pharmacies and sexually transmitted infections (STIs) (Kohler et al. 2017) and are like our findings. As in other low- and middle-income countries, pharmacy workers are in contact with a significant number of clients and respond to their needs for advice and even treatment for their health problems (Fathima et al. 2013). Despite regulatory efforts in LMICs (low- or middle-income countries), many prescription drugs are available without a prescription. Although these practices may not be “legal,” they fill a gap that exists in

the formal health care system, offering clients accessibility (“closer to home”), acceptability (clients perceive pharmacy workers as experts and unbiased), and affordability (no consultation fee) (Sarker et al. 2017). Pharmacies are businesses and are always looking for opportunities to sell drugs. However, pharmacy workers also believe they have a role in their community and want to do well (Steed L et al. 2019).

Pharmacies have also been reported to be the first point of contact for most TB patients, especially those in urban settings. For example, in Delhi, India, pharmacy workers were the first point of contact and provided clinical advice for 2/3 of TB patients (Kapoor et al. 2012). Unfortunately, studies attempting to identify and record the pathways followed by TB patients showed that almost none of the drug vendors referred probable TB patients directly to a health facility, causing delays in TB diagnosis and treatment (Kapoor et al. 2012; Sarker et al. 2017).

On the other hand, a study of diagnostic delays and associated factors among pulmonary TB patients in Tanzania found that patients living far from pharmacies were less likely to visit a health center. This may be related to recommendations given by pharmacies to seek treatment at a health center or to the availability of health services, which affects their use by residents (Mhalu G et al. 2019). There could be a social desirability bias in their reporting.

In Bolivia, an intervention to promote referrals from private pharmacies to the National Tuberculosis Strategy found a decrease in the proportion of pharmacies selling TB drugs and an increase in the percentage of pharmacies referring simulated clients seeking TB drugs to the National Tuberculosis Strategy, with patient referrals increasing from 22% to 58% after the intervention (Lambert et al. 2005). In Cambodia, pharmacies collaborating with the country’s National TB Strategy have been referring respiratory-symptomatic individuals to public health facilities for treatment since 2005. The Phnom Penh Municipal Health Department estimates that pharmacy-referred patients account for approximately 9% of all TB patients in Cambodia (Kwabla MP et al. 2022). The current evidence suggests that pharmaceutical care interventions can potentially improve treatment outcomes among patients with pulmonary TB; no definitive conclusion can be drawn given the low methodological quality of the included studies and lack of long-term follow-up data (Awad K et al. 2024).

A limitation of our study is that it was conducted only in one district in Lima and one in the north of the country, which may not represent what happens in the rest of Lima or Peru. In addition, we collected information from only one of the workers in each pharmacy, who reported what he/she thought happened during other shifts and estimated the number of clients coming to the pharmacy. Finally, the study was not developed to analyze associations. An important strength of this study is that it included most of the pharmacies in a district with one of the highest TB rates in northern Peru.

Conclusion

We found that pharmacy workers have adequate knowledge about TB, but with gaps and myths related to ways to prevent transmission. The level of TB knowledge of apothecary and pharmacy staff improved after an SMS text message-based intervention. Acceptance of this type of intervention is highly favorable.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted without any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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Institutional review board statement

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Ethics Committee of Hospital San Bartolomé, Lima, Peru.

Informed consent statement

Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study.

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